

CRITICAL HIT TO INNOVATION: WHY COMPETITION LAW MUST EMBRACE CREATIVITY IN GAMING

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Critical Hit to Innovation: Why Competition Law Must Embrace Creativity in Gaming

Sebastian Martin*

Outstanding LLM Dissertations 2025

Abstract

This paper critically examines competition law's current approach to innovation in the video gaming industry, arguing that its prevailing one-dimensional, outcome-focused framework – typically measured through R&D expenditure, patent activity, and content output – fails to capture the dynamics that genuinely promote competition and deliver value to gamers. It contends that the diversity, quality, and direction of innovation are equally important, and that these are best understood by accounting for the creativity and processes that underpin the sector. This is achieved by distinguishing between 'innovation' as the commercial implementation of novel products or methods, and 'creativity' as the original, often smaller, collaborative, and iterative processes that give rise to them, frequently driven by smaller competitors and users. This paper advances a 'creativity lens', incorporating creativity as a parameter of competition alongside traditional innovation metrics. This framework emphasises the openness, autonomy, and diversity of the creative processes through which games are made, modified, and distributed, prioritising the meaningful participation of users and indie studios. Applying a creativity lens to the *Microsoft/Activision Blizzard* merger demonstrates how an outcome-based focus overlooked harms to user creativity and indie studio innovation, particularly in the context of cloud gaming. This paper concludes that recognising creativity as a competitive factor better safeguards gamer welfare and fosters more meaningful, long-term innovation in the industry.

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1. Introduction

In gaming, competition law often equates 'more new content' with 'more innovation and competition'. However, this detaches from analysis the structural conditions and procedural freedoms that enable original creation and meaningful participation. These are inseparable from innovation: constraints on small game developers and user co-creation processes may leave prices unchanged whilst eroding the creativity and real innovations gamers value. Gaming is a 'creative industry', yet the competitive forces that impact it, and the harms that may arise, are not fully captured by traditional legal and economic metrics.

The global video game industry is economically and culturally influential: it is the largest creative entertainment sector,¹ estimated at almost \$355 billion.² The market is structured as a mix of dominant AAA studios and smaller independent ('indie') studios, the former with access to more money and resources. Uniquely, even though economic success is concentrated with AAA studios, indie games, and user mods can go from obscure releases to global hits virtually overnight, exerting competitive pressure on incumbents.³ This dynamic, rare in traditional markets, highlights how the creativity of indie studios and users is powerful and should be considered.

Despite the value generated by creative processes in gaming, competition law's metrics struggle to capture them, relying on outcomes instead. Patent activity and R&D spending are easier to measure, which increases legal certainty, with companies like Ubisoft appearing highly innovative.⁴ Yet an output-only focus can mask creative decline, with many of Ubisoft's titles criticised for repetitive formulas and glitchy releases. Consumers then become desperate for original titles like 'Schedule I' – made with a lower budget, but more creative. This disconnect exposes a regulatory blind spot in gaming; traditional metrics quantify innovation as output, not as quality, variety, or creative origin. Much of gaming's value arises from creative processes that do not register on competition's radar because they are hard to quantify or generate few patents.

¹ Ayse Yasar et al., 'Gaming Without Frontiers: Copyright and Competition in the Changing Video Game Sector' (CREATE Working Paper 2023/10, 2023), 4 <<https://eprints.gla.ac.uk/307648/2/307648.pdf>> accessed 10 July 2025.

² Jessica Clement, 'Video game industry - Statistics & Facts' (Statista, 6 November 2024) <<https://www.statista.com/topics/868/video-games/#topicOverview>> accessed 8 August 2025.

³ Smash JT, 'Schedule I Is Already More Popular Than Assassin's Creed Shadows...' (Smash JT, March 2025) <<https://www.smashjt.com/post/schedule-i-is-already-more-popular-than-assassin-s-creed-shadows>> accessed 9 July 2025.

⁴ Hilton Webster, 'How many games has Ubisoft made?' (TheGamer, 14 October 2024) <<https://www.thegamer.com/how-many-games-ubisoft-made/>> accessed 30 June 2025.

Against this, the sector remains largely unexamined,⁵ with past regulatory scrutiny occurring mainly through occasional merger reviews.⁶ Only recently has academic research begun to interrogate the relationship between innovation and creativity, notably by Thomas et al. in the context of cloud gaming, who frame it as an innovation-creativity dichotomy. Their work focuses on modding and virtual worlds, calling for a greater recognition of creative processes.⁷ This paper takes a similar stance but adopts a broader sectoral view beyond cloud gaming, considering other competitive elements such as the role of smaller, yet creativity-led, indie studios and users. It also suggests the adoption of a 'gamer welfare' standard and a 'creativity lens' to improve enforcement. This paper argues for going further than Thomas et al.'s ambiguous 'recalibration' of competition and consumer welfare,⁸ which leaves authorities likely reliant on more easily administrable output metrics. Our new analytical tools instead operationalise creativity as a dimension of competition in gaming, compelling regulators to evaluate process-level creativity alongside innovation outcomes.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides an overview of the gaming industry, then defines innovation and its relationship to competition. It assesses innovation in gaming and argues that competition law must move past its one-dimensional understanding of innovation as an outcome, also accounting for its innovation diversity, quality, and direction. Chapter 3 crystallises the concept of creativity and highlights the limits of innovation further by contrasting it with how creative processes should be considered as another metric. It is then demonstrated that gamers do care about creativity, not just innovation outcomes, by a case study of the concurrent release of two AAA and indie studio titles. Building on these insights, a 'creativity lens' is proposed for competition law, which enables authorities to better protect creativity and innovation's quality, diversity, and direction. Chapter 4 applies the creativity lens in practice through an analysis of *Microsoft/Activision Blizzard*.⁹ It re-examines the merger's implications for innovation by looking at two creative process dimensions overlooked in the official review – user creativity and indie studios. This analysis shows how a creativity-centric assessment might alter the enforcement narrative and illustrates

⁵ Yasar (n 1).

⁶ Alba Martinez, 'A Fortnite and Odd Days: The Console Wars' (2022) 6(2) MCLR 51, 52.

⁷ Amy Thomas et al., 'Competition in the cloud gaming market: proposing the innovation-creativity dichotomy' (2025) 8(2) IELR 1.

⁸ *ibid* 2.

⁹ CMA, '*Microsoft/Activision Blizzard* merger inquiry' (CMA Website, 6 July 2022) <<https://www.gov.uk/cma-cases/microsoft-slash-activision-blizzard-merger-inquiry>> accessed 29 July 2025.

the practical value and challenges of integrating a creativity lens into competition enforcement. Chapter 5 concludes.

Overall, this paper is a call to academics and regulators to recognise that not all innovation is equal. By critically examining it through a creativity lens, this study aims to contribute a more nuanced legal understanding – one that understands where gaming’s value stems from, and one that equips competition law to protect the next evolution of creative innovation.

2. Competition Law’s Current Focus on Innovation

This chapter argues that competition law’s current perspective on innovation and output is inadequate. It does not account for other parameters of innovation and overlooks the suppression of creative processes in gaming.

2.1. Overview of the Gaming Industry

Creative industries like gaming originate from creativity, skill, and talent, holding the potential for wealth creation through the generation and exploitation of intellectual property (IP).¹⁰ They rely on new technologies and individual creativity, producing goods that carry cultural and economic significance.¹¹ The incumbent producers are AAA studios, like ‘Activision’ and ‘Ubisoft’, dominating mainstream marketplaces with their large resource pool and mainstream games like ‘Call of Duty’. Contrastingly, indie studios produce niche titles but may also find commercial success. Usefully, Yasar et al. provide an overview of the industry’s actors.

¹⁰ Xavier Greffe, ‘Managing Creative Enterprises’ (WIPO Creative Industries Booklet No 3, December 2006), 10 <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/copyright/938/wipo_pub_938.pdf#:~:text=later%20when%20the%20product%20is,as%20well%20as%20their%20own> accessed 9 July 2025.

¹¹ *ibid* 10–11.

Figure 1: Key Games Sector Actors' in Ayse Yasar et al., 'Gaming Without Frontiers: Copyright and Competition in the Changing Video Game Sector' (CREATe Working Paper 2023/10, 2023).

Gaming is a diverse industry with users, or 'gamers', as central to the sector. Its key actors are interdependent on each other, but competition usually remains within their respective industries. To play video games, a device is required, provided by hardware manufacturers. Gamers must also purchase a game to play, offered through an overlap between 'developers' and 'publishers'. The marketplace historically consisted of physical shops, later taking a more digital distribution form through online purchases of digital games, but with gamers holding similar legal IP rights as before. More recently, cloud gaming subscriptions, akin to streaming services, have become prominent – gamers pay a cheaper price compared to full purchase and have access to an online library of games, but do not own any of them outright. The library handles the technical aspects of the game's execution on its servers and streams the video output to the user's device. Importantly, these services shift IP control back to platform owners and raise concerns that were overlooked in the *Microsoft/Activision* merger,¹² like the possibility of restricting creativity.

¹² *Microsoft/Activision Blizzard*(n 9).

Gaming has high fixed development costs but negligible marginal distribution costs, particularly via digital platforms. Therefore, a game can go from a niche indie release to a global hit overnight more easily than with physical shops.¹³ This is important for competition law as it means small firms generate considerable pressure on dominant firms as they may release a market-disrupting game at any time. This is a rare dynamic in traditional markets, and a reason indie firms require consideration during competition assessments due to the major disruptive and competitive forces their innovations can produce.

2.2. Defining Innovation

The consumer welfare standard refers to the benefits consumers derive from competitive markets, including elements like lower prices and higher quality.¹⁴ In many competition law jurisdictions it is used as the benchmark against which the effects of business practices and mergers are assessed. It improves with productive and allocative efficiencies – when goods are produced at the lowest cost and resources are optimally distributed. However, the exact definition of consumer welfare remains contested: some equate it strictly with consumer surplus, referring to the difference between the price they are willing to pay and do; others see it as a fluid concept shaped by the courts.¹⁵ This paper argues that although consumer surplus is usually synonymous with consumer welfare, it is fluid and can be developed. A ‘gamer welfare’ standard will be argued as preferable, better capturing the nuances of gaming’s markets and its consumers.

Innovation, or dynamic efficiency, is a parameter of competition, focusing on technological progress and product variety, not just static price effects.¹⁶ Nonetheless, it still has the power to drive prices down and quality up.¹⁷ For competition purposes, the OECD defines it as ‘the successful development and application of new knowledge’.¹⁸ A frequently made distinction is between ‘product’ and ‘process’ innovations, separated by their magnitude of market effect as

¹³ Ritwik Mitra, ‘Indie Games that Became Major Success Stories’ (30 December 2024) <<https://gamerant.com/indie-games-major-success-stories/>> accessed 9 July 2025.

¹⁴ OECD, ‘The Consumer Welfare Standard - Advantages and Disadvantages Compared to Alternative Standards (Background Note, 25 April 2023), 11 <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP\(2023\)4/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP(2023)4/en/pdf)> accessed 7 August 2025.

¹⁵ ICN, ‘Competition Enforcement and Consumer Welfare’ (ICN Conference, Hague, May 2011), 20 <https://www.internationalcompetitionnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/SP_CWelfare2011.pdf> accessed 2 August 2025.

¹⁶ See e.g., C-413/14 *Intel v Commission* [2017] OJ C374/2, [134]; European Commission, ‘Guidelines on the applicability of Article 101 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union to horizontal co-operation agreements’ [2023] OJ C259/1, footnote 29.

¹⁷ Gönenç Gürkaynak, *Innovation Paradox in Merger Control* (1st ed, Concurrences 2023), 28.

¹⁸ Aura Pabón, Antonio Capobianco, ‘Competition and Innovation, Part I: a theoretical perspective’ (Background Note, 2 May 2023), 6 <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP\(2023\)2/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP(2023)2/en/pdf)> accessed 9 July 2025.

big 'breakthrough' innovations or smaller 'incremental' ones.¹⁹ Crucially, as the Oslo Manual highlights, 'innovation requires implementation' – it is an outcome, not just the creative processes leading to it.²⁰ Still, as the next chapter argues, those processes remain important to gaming, forming a parameter of competition linked to, but distinct from innovation.

Creativity as a process can be understood as both a pre-innovation condition, requiring legal sensitivity, and as a mechanism, which consumers value. The line between the creative process and innovation in gaming is often blurred, as the output is also often creative. The focus with creative processes is the act of creating itself; innovation is concerned with the implementation of new ideas that bring value. An example of an important creative process which can lead to innovations is modding, where users alter a game's code.²¹ It provides additions gamers value, like free content or glitch fixes. This is particularly relevant as many games, particularly those produced by major studios, are constrained by tight development timeframes. They consequently launch with unresolved glitches, with user modding acting as a form of post-launch quality control.²²

More significantly, mods like 'Dota' can ultimately become commercialised innovations and global bestsellers, pro-competitively disrupting market structures and generating incumbent pressure.²³ This demonstrates how beneficial a creative process often pursued by consumers can be, leading to innovations that reshape gaming from within. Yet, Schumpeter argues that structural economic changes remain driven by innovation, not consumer processes. He identified five developmental stages, with innovations leading to changes in market structure – often through the 'creative destruction' of monopolies by breakthrough innovations.²⁴ However, this paper contends that such a view is too narrow, leading competition assessments in gaming to only focus on high-tech developments like cloud gaming. Incremental innovations, akin to modding, also enhance consumer welfare, even if they do not reshape markets.

Admittedly, breakthrough innovations like cloud gaming remain more competitively important, benefitting consumers and disrupting incumbents by creating new markets and business

¹⁹ *ibid* 6.

²⁰ OECD/EuroStat, 'Oslo Manual 2018' (4th ed, OECD Publishing 2018) <https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2018/10/oslo-manual-2018_g1g9373b/9789264304604-en.pdf> accessed 9 July 2025.

²¹ Thomas (n 7) 21.

²² Mary Osborne, 'Cyberpunk 2077 Fans Are Fixing The Game Themselves' (SVG, 8 February 2021) <<https://www.svg.com/329720/cyberpunk-2077-fans-are-fixing-the-game-themselves/>> accessed 4 August 2025.

²³ Mike Stubbs, 'The incredible rise of Dota' (Red Bull, 30 July 2019) <<https://www.redbull.com/int-en/the-history-of-dota>> accessed 2 August 2025.

²⁴ Gürkaynak (n 17) 24.

models. Yet, this does not reduce the importance of incrementality, especially in gaming. As the studio 'FromSoftware' shows with 'Dark Souls', gamers can value it more than breakthroughs. Small but carefully calculated game design, adhering to a game's core mechanics but incrementally innovating storytelling and world design, leads to undeniable impacts on gaming.²⁵ This paper therefore adopts a broad view, recognising both breakthrough and incremental innovations as key to understanding the significance of different innovations in gaming.

2.3. The Relationship Between Competition and Innovation

The relationship between competition and innovation is hard to pinpoint – it is not consistent in terms of cause-and-effect, nor is it always correlated in intensity.²⁶ What is known is that competition treats innovation as a non-price parameter, alongside quality and choice, its prominence having increased alongside transformational developments like digitalisation and globalisation.²⁷ It is a key driver of competition and especially relevant to creative industries, as its creative outputs are unique and non-routine, but can be subject to unpredictable consumer demand. As Greffe notes, 'nobody knows' how a new cultural product will be received.²⁸ Innovation is therefore important for competition, yet it remains difficult to capture, leaving uncertainty over which regulatory approach authorities should adopt.

Schumpeter would argue that oligopolies are best suited for innovation: their incumbents have the resources for risky R&D.²⁹ Therefore, gaming's innovations are best facilitated by allowing one or two dominant firms to pursue all innovation. A lenient enforcement approach, allowing for more anti-competitive practices, incentivises firms to innovate and secure IP rights – creating temporary legal monopolies because the resulting 'creative destruction' will revolutionise markets.³⁰ This paper believes this approach is ill-suited to gaming, prioritising large-scale breakthrough innovations but missing the incremental innovations previously argued to be valuable. The emphasis on structural market changes undervalues the cumulative impact of incremental innovations like mods, generated by creative processes.

²⁵ Dylan Burt, 'FromSoftware's Influence: A Legacy of Challenge and Discovery' (Brig Newspaper, 7 March 2025) <<https://brignews.com/2025/03/07/fromsoftwares-influence-a-legacy-of-challenge-and-discovery/>> accessed 9 July 2025.

²⁶ OECD, 'The Relationship Between Competition and Innovation' (BIAC Note, 14 June 2023), 4 <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD\(2023\)56/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD(2023)56/en/pdf)> accessed 9 July 2025.

²⁷ European Commission, 'Review of the Merger Guidelines: Topic C' (EC Website, 2025) <https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/mergers/review-merger-guidelines_en> accessed 5 July 2025.

²⁸ Greffe (n 10) 8.

²⁹ Joseph Schumpeter, *Capitalism, Socialism, and Democracy* (1st ed, Routledge 2003), 84-85 <<https://periferiaactiva.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/joseph-schumpeter-capitalism-socialism-and-democracy-2006.pdf>> accessed 9 August 2025.

³⁰ *ibid* 83.

Contrastingly, Arrow maintains that atomistic competition is the engine of innovation, as oligopolies lack the competitive pressure to pursue innovation because they control the consumer base.³¹ In gaming, this implies more enforcement against incumbents so that many small studios, racing to outperform each other, better drive innovation. With this, the issue is that because competition is near-perfect, any innovations will be quickly overtaken by another, reducing the overall incentive to create new products. Aghion offers a middle ground: an inverted U-shaped relationship where moderate competition drives innovation.³² In gaming, this appears to be the current structure - a mix of incumbents and indie studios who share the market at approximately 50% each by revenue.³³ The danger is that this dynamic is threatened by developments like cloud gaming, positive from an innovation focus, but which can entrench the market positions of incumbents and restrict gaming's overall innovation pipeline, fuelled by creative processes.

The actual approach taken by authorities towards innovation has been mixed, but, as the European Commission (EC) notes, Europe has struggled to keep pace with other major economies due to a lack of it.³⁴ Regulatory burden is blamed as a primary reason for this lack of growth, also seen in the UK.³⁵ In response, reports have argued that boosting competitiveness requires closing the innovation gap through deregulation and simplification.³⁶ This shift, however, risks leaning towards a Schumpeterian model that favours dominant firms. Whilst deregulation might attract investment, and support technological progress, it is an incomplete solution which is unsatisfactory for gaming. Regulation plays a vital role in preserving competition and managing IP rights, crucial for creative risk-taking. A permissive approach spurs short-term innovation but entrenches market power, leading to long-term harm. Striking the right balance and not rushing towards deregulation is therefore essential to continue to foster valuable creative innovations. Cloud gaming represents this critical juncture between innovation and competition. As a breakthrough process innovation, it has achieved 'creative

³¹ Antonio Capobianco, 'The Relationship between Competition and Innovation' (Note by Austria, 14 June 2023), 2 <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD\(2023\)5/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD(2023)5/en/pdf)> accessed 9 July 2025.

³² Philippe Aghion et al., 'Competition and Innovation: An Inverted-U Relationship (2005) 120(2) QJE 701.

³³ Video Game Insights, 'Global Indie Games Market Report 2024' (VGInsights, 13 October 2024), 4 <https://vginsights.com/assets/reports/VGI_Global_Indie_Games_Market_Report_2024.pdf> accessed 21 July 2025.

³⁴ European Commission, 'A Competitiveness Compass for the EU' (Communication, 29 January 2025), 1 <https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/10017eb1-4722-4333-add2-e0ed18105a34_en?filename=Communication_1.pdf> accessed 2 August 2025.

³⁵ *ibid* 16; Simon Jack, Charlotte Edwards, 'Government ousts UK competition watchdog chair' (BBC, 21 January 2025) <<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/c2d3e6zklxg>> accessed 1 July 2025.

³⁶ Mario Draghi, 'The future of European competitiveness' (Part A, 9 September 2024), 6 <https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/97e481fd-2dc3-412d-be4c-f152a8232961_en?filename=The%20future%20of%20European%20competitiveness%20-%20A%20competitiveness%20strategy%20for%20Europe.pdf> accessed 2 August 2025.

destruction' by altering markets and introducing new business models. Nevertheless, it risks creating bottlenecks around distribution platforms and infrastructure, dominant firms then controlling these new value chains. They may restrict market access for indie developers or other major companies, suppressing innovation and creativity despite the appearance of greater consumer choice. Ergo, deregulation alone is insufficient to address these concerns.

The relationship between innovation and competition is complex, and a 'one-size-fits-all' approach is unsustainable. Fostering innovation requires allowing some scale to emerge but necessitates vigilance against market-foreclosing practices. Competition enforcement must be tailored to gaming's unique dynamics and account for broader factors driving innovation in gaming, such as IP rights, user contributions, and creative processes. Whether innovation is driven by oligopoly or competition, both theories overlook the process-level suppression of creativity that may arise in gaming.

2.4. Assessing Innovation in Gaming

In gaming, flawed measures of the competition-innovation relationship risk overlooking harm to competition. This section critiques the dominant output-based innovation measure used in gaming, which overlooks the also important dimensions of innovation, like diversity, quality, and direction.

Two metrics of innovation are R&D expenditure and patent activity.³⁷ The former is an input-measure, usually considered as a proportion to total revenue (R&D intensity) and the latter an output-measure, calculated through the number of patent requests or grants; both methods have drawbacks. Input metrics demonstrate a firm's commitment to creative innovation and can be tracked financially. However, spending does not necessarily equate to creative outputs valued by consumers. As shown in the next chapter, Ubisoft's high-budget release was outsold by a one-person indie studio, highlighting how low-cost creativity can outperform expensive innovation, yet remain invisible to such measures. Focusing on output is also flawed, patent activity offering a quantifiable recognition of innovation but potentially constituting an expensive process, too costly for indie studios and therefore not capturing all market innovation. Measuring product output avoids this issue but equates quantity with innovation quality, which does not always hold in creative industries, as the Ubisoft example further shows.

What all these approaches share is a focus on outcome, mirrored in the dominant approach by competition assessments, with little discussion of innovation quality. In *Dow/DuPont*³⁸ and

³⁷ Pabón (n 18) 7.

³⁸ COMP/M.7932 *Dow/DuPont* [2017] OJ C353/9.

*Bayer/Monsanto*³⁹ an innovation-sensitive theory of harm was used, highlighting the adverse effects of the mergers on the parties' incentives to invest in closely related innovation paths pre-merger. Yet, because innovation competition was understood as an output-maximising device, there was no analysis regarding the impact the merger would have on the diversity, quality, or direction of innovation.⁴⁰ More recently, this trend has continued in gaming, regulators focusing on whether vertical integration and exclusivity would limit access to competing games on cloud platforms – an outcome.⁴¹ They overlooked how cloud gaming impacts IP rights, modding, and user-generated content, other key creativity drivers. There was no discussion on diversity, quality, or direction, just outcomes. Unlike the farmers in *Dow/DuPont*, gamers do not consume a fungible product in a market where innovation only affects price; games are purchased to play over multiple hours, and gamer engagement relies on originality and diversity. Taking the same approach to gaming innovation as other markets neglects the creativity that generates gaming's value.

Undoubtedly, measuring innovation this way is harder, and risks mission creep. Competition law, especially considering the recent deregulation agenda, is pressured to use hardline econometrics to protect markets, not abstract or subjective concepts like 'creativity'. However, this paper argues that market power in gaming not only affects innovation output but can also be exercised against the creative processes leading to it. Dominant firms can foreclose modding communities, block interoperable tools and lock developers into digital ecosystems. Anti-competitive actors are shaping not just market outcomes, but the direction of gaming through creative process harms. An output-centred conceptualisation of innovation fails to capture gaming's market definitions and consumer effects properly. Creative industries, by their inherent characteristics, necessitate an assessment of innovation diversity, quality, and direction.

2.5. Moving Past a One-Dimensional Understanding of Innovation

Before discussing how a process-outcome approach better assesses innovation, a proposed method of doing so is with a creativity-sensitive technical-artistic innovation dichotomy, focusing instead on the nature of the innovation. Technical innovations include tangible advances in technology, like cloud gaming; artistic innovations reflect the creative processes and outcomes linked to less tangible, but equally vital, elements like modding. This acknowledges that innovation is not one-dimensional in gaming and competition law, measured

³⁹ COMP/M.8084 *Bayer/Monsanto* [2018] 1709 final.

⁴⁰ Elias Deutscher, Stavros Makris, 'Sustainability concerns in EU merger control: from output-maximising to polycentric innovation competition' (2023) 11 JAE 350, 354.

⁴¹ *Microsoft/Activision Blizzard* (n 9).

by output, but that innovations can be technical or creative. More diverse innovation types may be accounted for whilst still relying on observable criteria.

However, conflating process and outcome under this dichotomy has limitations. It is difficult to ensure that both types are afforded equal regulatory weight in analysis, especially in enforcement contexts where authorities are under institutional and political pressure to avoid perceptions of overreach. The EU's 'more economic approach' reinforces this by prioritising quantifiable indicators over subjective, qualitative dimensions like artistic or creative value. Dunne notes that this focus on anti-competitive foreclosure, backed by quantifiable econometric assessments, has disclaimed any role for broader public interest considerations,⁴² which would include the subjective value some gamers place on creativity. If measurable outcomes are available in lieu of subjective value judgements, these are likely to dominate analysis of both technical and artistic innovations, sidelining the less tangible but equally important processes that drive innovation in creative industries. Regulators' decisions are more convincingly backed by output statistics, instead of judgements regarding how much consumers value 'creativity'.

To address this problem, a polycentric understanding of innovation and competition, as advanced by Deutscher and Makris, offers a more robust foundation. Polycentricity refers to processes of social organisation that are structured around many decision-making centres which are formally independent of one another, but they choose to act in ways that account for each other.⁴³ Despite the article's focus on sustainability, it can be applied analogously to the gaming sector. Innovation competition should not be viewed solely as output-maximising, but as a polycentric process where independent decision makers pursue various innovation paths, better accounting for innovation's diversity, quality, and direction.⁴⁴ Diverse actors like users, indie studios, and AAA developers pursue various innovation paths and creative processes. Yet, they are interconnected, and an output-only focus is unsatisfactory; authorities must take account of their processes, and what they contribute to innovation's other dimensions, during assessment. As Lianos agrees, the increasing interdependence of various spheres of social activity and the emergence of large platforms in the digital economy may bring the traditional competition law approach of price and output effects closer to a polycentric model.⁴⁵

⁴² Niamh Dunne, 'Public Interest and EU Competition Law' (2020) 65(2) *The Antitrust Bulletin* 256, 260.

⁴³ Deutscher, Stavros (n 40) 377.

⁴⁴ *ibid* 354.

⁴⁵ Ioannis Lianos, 'Polycentric Competition Law' (2018) 71(1) *Current Legal Problems* 161, 165.

This approach is less controversial considering the recent practices of the EU and UK authorities, focusing on wider digital economy issues. Digital market legislation has been asymmetric, applying to digital gatekeeper firms with substantial market power, and focused on interoperability, contestability, and wider consumer harms.⁴⁶ This reveals a shift away from traditional methods, and a new focus on the pre-conditions of innovation. Competition does not need to rely on the orthodox but can adapt to continue to protect competition and consumers. Not doing the same in gaming risks inadequate enforcement. A full understanding of innovation includes the processes,⁴⁷ which in gaming are the diverse range of creativity resulting in valuable gaming innovations.

Polycentricity thus supports the incorporation of creative processes as legitimate in gaming. By recognising that innovation arises from multiple sources of creativity, polycentricity demands that competition enforcement look beyond output and instead safeguard gaming's diverse innovation contributors. Accordingly, an approach that fails to engage with these competitive dynamics risks entrenching dominant firms, overlooking anti-competitive practices that marginalise creativity, and neglecting harms to the quality, diversity, and direction of innovation. A polycentric model is therefore not merely descriptive but prescriptive, guiding regulators to foster the pluralism, openness, and creative autonomy needed to sustain innovation in gaming by looking beyond it as purely output-maximising.

3. The Importance of Creative Processes in Gaming

As established, the dominant competition parameter of creative market analysis has been innovation. This chapter defines creativity, substantiates the claim that gamers do care about creativity and that competition law should too. It then demonstrates why process matters and argues that a creativity lens should be introduced, improving competition enforcement by enabling the consideration of creativity and innovation's diversity, quality, and direction.

3.1. What is Creativity?

'Creativity' and 'innovation' lack specific legal meanings and a clear relationship, leading to debate on how they relate. Christie contends that not all creativity leads to innovation as the distinction lies in the novelty of the outcome, innovation being a subset of creation which

⁴⁶ Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act) [2022] OJ L 265/1.

⁴⁷ Lianos (n 45) 183.

involves creating something that had not previously existed.⁴⁸ But as the use of ‘innovation’ and ‘creativity’ varies between disciplines, their meaning is likely purposive. For gaming, this paper proposes to separate the two based on ‘original creative process/input’ and ‘novel innovation outcome’. ‘Creativity’ is the process which generates original ideas, including the activities of experimentation, risk-taking and iteration,⁴⁹ evincing the free and creative choices of creators but not requiring commercialisation. ‘Innovation’ entails implementing these concepts into commercialised novel products or processes, usually leading to wealth creation.⁵⁰ Recognising creativity and innovation as distinct affects the way they are treated. As commonly known in IP, patent law applies to innovations, requiring novelty, inventiveness, and applicability; copyright law protects original works, but does not compel novelty. One can independently create a work nearly identical to an existing one and still enjoy copyright protection, provided that it was not copied.

This divergence illustrates that the law already relies on a separation of creativity and innovation. Originality is about the process and source of expression; novelty relates to the outcome. Positioning creativity as a subset of innovation, per Christie, collapses this important distinction. As discussed later, focusing on creativity also allows for a more nuanced assessment of innovation: incorporating process in analysis does not just highlight creativity; it enhances how innovation is understood. It expands its parameters from output to include its quality, diversity, and direction, allowing regulators to evaluate not just whether innovation is occurring, but whether competition law is supporting the creative processes that lead to it. Christie was correct that not all creativity will lead to innovation – but this is due to it being a process, not a subset, of innovation.⁵¹ Collapsing the two risks undervaluing the creative processes consumers value.

3.2. Do Gamers Value Creativity?

This section explores gamer perspectives and evidence supporting that gamers care about creativity. Therefore, including creative processes in analysis and the later-discussed creativity lens is justified.

⁴⁸ Andrew Christie, ‘Creativity and Innovation: A Legal Perspective’ in Leon Mann and Janet Chan (eds), *Creativity and Innovation in Business and Beyond: Social Science Perspectives and Policy Implications* (1st ed, Routledge 2011) 104.

⁴⁹ Mauricio Castillo-Vergara et al., ‘The Creative Process and Innovation: The Role of Knowledge Management and Industrial Cluster’ (2022) 26(6) IJIM 1.

⁵⁰ David Cropley et al., ‘Measuring Creativity for Innovation Management’ (2011) 6(3) JTMI 14, 14.

⁵¹ Christie (n 48) 105.

Related gaming literature supports that creativity is something consumers value. As Zackariasson and Wilson note, indie developer Schafer sourced more than \$1 million in less than 24 hours from gamers to develop his next game. Some argue that this funding stemmed from 'a growing pent-up demand for really good, creatively designed games that aren't coming out of the big publishers'.⁵² This signals two things: users are both providers and users of value in gaming, and creativity is a demand not being currently met. This raises the question of why the market is not delivering what consumers want, and which law is best suited to help? One could argue that creativity-related harms should fall within the scope of consumer protection, as creative harms are not competitive harms. However, this paper submits that this underestimates the broader structural impact that creativity has on competition. Instead of market power leading to traditionally anti-competitive exclusionary practices, creative harms manifest themselves through quasi-exploitative effects: consumer manipulation and the erosion of creativity. These undermine the competitive processes that make the gaming industry culturally valuable. Creativity is a competitive force, driving differentiation and market dynamism, disrupting the dominance of bigger studios as shown by 'TVGS v Ubisoft' later.

It is well-known that harmful market structures producing negative consumer effects form a legitimate basis for antitrust involvement. Therefore, if gamers care about creativity, threats to it support the involvement of competition law. As White observes, Microsoft, Sony, and Nintendo each operate proprietary console ecosystems. They can control not only pricing and distribution, but also the rules of creative participation.⁵³ Gatekeeper power and platform control can suppress creative entrants and reinforce homogenised content within an already concentrated market. Indeed, some literature already cites the console industry as an oligopoly, where major players can strategically avoid disruptive competition.⁵⁴ Creativity is a disruptive force gamers care about, and its pro-competitive effects must be fostered to their benefit. Centring analysis on innovation outcomes fails to capture the degradation of creativity, particularly where dominant firms can exercise market power to exacerbate creative harms. The outcome is not merely reduced innovation, but what scholars have termed a 'senescence of creativity' – a market environment in which the conditions necessary for original and meaningful creation are increasingly choked off.⁵⁵

⁵² Peter Zackariasson, Timothy Wilson, 'The Role of the Consumer: From Sales to Co-production' in Sabine Hotho and Neil McGregor (eds), *Changing the Rules of the Game* (1st ed, Palgrave Macmillan 2013), 48.

⁵³ Matthew White, 'The Senescence of Creativity: How Market Forces are Killing Digital Games' (2009) 3(4) *Loading...*, 2 <<https://journals.sfu.ca/loading/index.php/loading/article/view/54>> accessed 29 July 2025.

⁵⁴ William Forgang, Karl Einolf, *Management Economics: An Accelerated Approach* (1st ed, Routledge 2015), 159.

⁵⁵ White (n 53).

3.2.1. TVGS v Ubisoft Case Study

Since its inception in 1986, Ubisoft has released approximately 530 games. Roughly one a month, this appears as a highly innovative and pro-competitive entity when measured by output.⁵⁶ Yet, Ubisoft has been consistently criticised for releasing games with widespread glitches,⁵⁷ and repetitive gameplay.⁵⁸ Many releases revolve around franchises like 'Assassin's Creed', resulting in recycled gameplay mechanics. Its creative stagnation has been met with increasing consumer frustration, with one writer suggesting that a publisher once known for its creativity and trend-setting has become risk-averse, pressured to maintain its empire by churning out unoriginal releases.⁵⁹ As another writer noted: 'Ubisoft wasn't just another developer; they had a knack for creating unique, memorable experiences' but eventually succumbed to 'franchise fatigue'.⁶⁰ Whilst any business is intrinsically pressured to keep its shareholders happy, Ubisoft has lost the creativity which fuelled its rise and that its players valued.

These issues are compounded by Ubisoft's microtransactions, a supposed innovation which allows players to buy digital items with real money. Whilst optional payments for in-game content are not inherently problematic, Ubisoft intentionally makes certain items difficult or impossible to earn through gameplay, compelling players to buy them. When Ubisoft's medieval fighting game 'For Honor' was released, one player estimated it would take over 2.5 years of casual play to unlock everything,⁶¹ or they could pay £610 on top of the game's original price of £55.⁶² Ubisoft's latest title, 'Assassin's Creed Shadows', continues this trend as the 14th game in the franchise, offering content only unlockable by paying.⁶³ This is not a critique of Ubisoft's business strategies, rather, it illustrates a key point: not all forms of 'innovation' are valued by

⁵⁶ Webster (n 4).

⁵⁷ Leo Kelion, 'Assassin's Creed: Unity criticised for widespread glitches' (BBC, 13 November 2014) <<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/technology-30040613>> accessed 30 June 2025.

⁵⁸ Anthony Marcusa, 'I'm tired of Ubisoft selling me the same game over and over' (Pocket-lint, 6 September 2024) <<https://www.pocket-lint.com/im-tired-of-ubisoft-selling-me-the-same-game-over-and-over/>> accessed 30 June 2025.

⁵⁹ Allen Julizar, 'How Ubisoft Lost Its Way - A Gamer's Lament and a Business Lesson For Us' (Medium, 8 October 2024) <<https://allenherlambang.medium.com/how-ubisoft-lost-its-way-a-gamers-lament-and-a-business-lesson-for-us-2956ee44049b>> accessed 1 July 2025.

⁶⁰ *ibid.*

⁶¹ Kyle Orland, 'Analysis: For Honor unlocks cost \$730 (or 5,200 hours)' (ArsTechnica, 21 March 2017) <<https://arstechnica.com/gaming/2017/03/analysis-for-honor-unlocks-cost-730-or-5200-hours/>> accessed 30 June 2025.

⁶² *ibid.*; MCV Staff, 'For Honor: Everything you need to know' (MCVUK, 3 February 2017) <<https://mcvuk.com/business-news/publishing/for-honor-everything-you-need-to-know-release-date-price-beta-and-season-pass-info-merchandise-and-pre-order-deals/>> accessed 30 June 2025.

⁶³ Angshuman Dutta, 'Does Assassin's Creed Shadows Feature Microtransactions?' (DeltiasGaming, 21 March 2025) <<https://deltiasgaming.com/does-assassins-creed-shadows-feature-microtransactions/>> accessed 1 July 2025.

consumers, especially when core content is locked behind paywalls, and innovation is reduced to superficial updates.

Contrastingly, 'Schedule I', a drug-dealing simulator released by TVGS at approximately the same time as Assassin's Creed Shadows, was produced by a solo indie developer with no marketing budget and likely a few hundred dollars in production costs. Whilst not as polished, it leaned into original engaging gameplay and content, priced at £16.75,⁶⁴ compared to Assassin's Creed's £59.99.⁶⁵ Despite its financial constraints, Schedule I achieved remarkable success, with the reception amongst gamers indicative of the reality of the gaming sector: consumers value creative, original experiences. Assassin's Creed Shadows had 64,825 players at its all-time peak in the last 3 months and a 77.80% positive feedback rate on Steam, the dominant PC platform. Contrastingly, Schedule I had a peak of 459,075 and a positive feedback rate of 97.16%.⁶⁶ This is not to say that all gamers want unique games every year, or that AAA studios cannot be creative. This is reflected by the continuing sales success of long-term, non-original games like 'Call of Duty'. But a creativity focus does not penalise large studios per se, instead protecting and fostering genuine creativity and diverse, quality innovation – whatever its source. It better captures what traditional innovation metrics miss: structural barriers and conduct that harms creative production and participation. Schedule I is evidence that games which focus on creativity can outperform gaming giants, mirrored by the larger industry trend that indie games have been generating as much revenue as larger studios on Steam.⁶⁷

The contrast between Ubisoft and TVGS is more than anecdotal. It illustrates that superficially, gaming is innovative and competitive: Ubisoft faces rival publishers, operates at scale, and sells products at competitive prices. Yet a creativity perspective reveals deeper structural concerns, with large firms such as Ubisoft and the later-discussed *Microsoft/Activision Blizzard* in a position to harm creativity in gaming. This is catalysed by the fact that the above companies also control their own gaming ecosystems and digital distribution platforms. They are more risk-averse and their profit focus risks them leveraging their platform power to foreclose real creativity, for fear of losing market share. Indie studios and, as seen later, users, are well placed to counter this stagnation, contributing both their own creativity to the market and a competitive pressure on incumbents, forcing them to do the same. Indeed, the indie market is

⁶⁴ SteamDB, 'Schedule I Steam Statistics' (SteamDB, 30 June 2025) <<https://steamdb.info/app/3164500/>> accessed 30 June 2025.

⁶⁵ SteamDB, 'Assassin's Creed Shadows Steam Statistics' (SteamDB, 30 June 2025) <<https://steamdb.info/app/3159330/charts/>> accessed 30 June 2025.

⁶⁶ SteamDB, (n 64, 66).

⁶⁷ Video Game Insights (n 33) 4.

the only one that continues to grow despite the industry's wider slowdown.⁶⁸ Admittedly, indie creativity may not always triumph over the AAA studio content-pump, but saliently, they may not be given the fair chance to do so. Indie developers, vectors of disruptive creativity, face marginalisation not due to a lack of merit, but because current market structures and legal frameworks fail to adequately protect creative processes, evincing why they must be accounted for.

3.3. Why Process Matters

As this paper has shown, when assessing innovation, authorities tend to focus on tangible outputs to evince innovation.⁶⁹ This approach is suited to industries like pharmaceuticals, where progress is driven by scientific R&D, tangible metrics ensuring legal certainty and justifying enforcement decisions. In gaming, value creation is as much creative as technical, and the output-based model misrepresents how value is created and experienced. There are two other factors relevant to innovation: who owns the assets and means of distribution, and the creative processes leading to it.⁷⁰ The prior two dimensions have featured in competition case law, but creative processes, the subject of this chapter, have been largely ignored.

As mentioned, in *Dow/DuPont* the EC was focused on innovation output, not the processes leading to it, with the same occurring in *Microsoft/Activision*, as discussed in the next chapter. The case law has focused on outcomes like reduced innovation and distribution harms, overlooking the creative processes underpinning gaming innovation. Scholars mirror this gap, noting that research measuring the effect of acquisitions on innovation tends to analyse outcomes like turnover or patent activity.⁷¹ Still, perhaps measuring outcomes nevertheless indirectly reflects creativity – patents require something 'extra' or 'original', thus creative input. A focus on outcome indirectly evinces successful creative processes, eliminating the need for a new approach. But in gaming, consumers value more than just output: like IP law, they distinguish between novel innovations and original creativity.

Moreover, patent applications play a less prominent role in industries like gaming; innovation instead arising from collaborative creative processes that are later developed into new products.⁷² Especially as the industry shifts towards subscription-based models, engagement

⁶⁸ *ibid* 8.

⁶⁹ Pabón (n 18) 7.

⁷⁰ Yasar (n 1) 16.

⁷¹ Masakazu Ishihara, Joost Rietveld, 'The Effect of Acquisitions on Product Innovativeness, Quality, and Sales Performance: Evidence from the Console Video Game Industry (2002-2010)' (2017) 1 *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 3 <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2897264> accessed 29 July 2025.

⁷² *ibid*.

and longevity will outweigh momentary sales, supporting a view that diverse and quality innovation, fuelled by creativity, is as important as output.⁷³ Traditional innovation frameworks, suited to brick-and-mortar markets, cannot capture this, and moving towards other approaches, such as ‘gamer welfare’ and the later proposed ‘creativity lens’ is desirable.

A useful analogy pertaining to the importance of process comes from sports. Typically, competition law prioritises the ‘competitive balance’ in matches: the idea that the playing strength of all the teams in a sports league is evenly matched. Fans are in enough doubt about the probable outcome of each game and will remain interested in watching, supporting television and ticket revenue.⁷⁴ This is supported by cases noting it as an objective to be protected in sports.⁷⁵ Yet, fan engagement is not driven just by who wins; it is also the processes occurring during the entire season: fantasy leagues, rivalries, and parallel tournaments. In response, a ‘fan welfare’ paradigm has emerged, advocating for the inclusion of the experiential and procedural dimensions of fandom, critical to properly understanding the sports market.⁷⁶ Indeed, fans are still ‘consumers’ in sports so some may argue it is better to persist with consumer welfare, protecting them by championing higher output and lower prices.⁷⁷ But it is precisely this focus on outcome that makes it unsuited for sports; fan welfare moves beyond it, and regulators gain a superior understanding of competition due to improved market assessments.

By analogy, this paper arrives at ‘gamer welfare’. Gamers care about processes like modding, invisible under a traditional innovation or consumer welfare approach. As a user-led creative process, modding extends a game’s lifespan and fills gameplay gaps developers missed. It can even lead to global successes: ‘Counter-Strike’, a multi-million player game, began as a mod for another.⁷⁸ The value of this process is not just abstract, reflected by one modding platform serving over 64 million users and paying out more than \$13 million to creators.⁷⁹ It is a player-led

⁷³ Ali Hussain, ‘How the Video Game Industry Is Changing’ (Investopedia, 26 April 2025) <<https://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/053115/how-video-game-industry-changing.asp>> accessed 28 July 2025.

⁷⁴ Salil Mehra, Joel Zuercher, ‘Striking Out “Competitive Balance” in Sports, Antitrust, and Intellectual Property’ (2006) 21(4) BTLJ 1499, 1500.

⁷⁵ C-519/04 *Meca-Medina and Majcen v Commission* [2006] ECR I-06991, [43].

⁷⁶ Oliver Budzinski, Arne Feddersen, ‘Should Organising Premier-Level European Football Be A Monopoly? And Who Should Run It? – An Economists’ Perspective’ in Jacob Kornbeck (ed), *EU Antitrust Law and Sport Governance* (1st ed, Routledge 2022), 88.

⁷⁷ Antonio Capobianco, ‘Advantages and Disadvantages of Competition Welfare Standards’ (Note by BIAC, 15 June 2023), 6 <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD\(2023\)30/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD(2023)30/en/pdf)> accessed 31 July 2025.

⁷⁸ Eric von Hippel, ‘The User Innovation Revolution’ (MIT Sloan Management Review Interview, 21 September 2011) <<https://sloanreview.mit.edu/article/the-user-innovation-revolution/>> accessed 2 July 2025.

⁷⁹ Nexus, ‘Nexus Mods’ (Nexus Mods Homepage, Statistics from 26 July 2025) <<https://www.nexusmods.com>> accessed 26 July 2025.

response to market gaps, also acting as a competitive force, and, as will be discussed regarding the creative stagnation of gaming innovation, it represents a call for more meaningful and original design. Yet, modding is invisible in standard competition assessments, generating few patents and seldom appearing in R&D budgets. This underscores the significance of gamer welfare and a creativity lens. Like fan welfare, they capture the other important dimensions of consumer value and enhance enforcement.

3.4. Creativity Lens

Thus far, this paper has demonstrated that innovation as output is an imperfect metric, gamers value creativity, and a process-based approach is best suited to capture that. Therefore, this paper proposes adopting a 'creativity lens' – a competition framework that values not only innovation's outcomes (price and quantity), but also its diversity, quality, and direction. It does this by focusing on the openness, autonomy, and diversity of the creative processes through which games are made, modified, and distributed.

A 'lens' refers to a framework through which the law is analysed and applied. For instance, an 'inclusivity lens' has been recommended in response to the systemic underrepresentation and inequitable treatment of certain demographic groups in gig-economy markets in competition law.⁸⁰ The markets were not captured accurately: Black and Latinx workers were overrepresented in categories of work with lower wages, fewer protections and greater instability.⁸¹ This lens meant considering how these sub-groups were affected by competition, something consumer welfare fails to do. Adopting new lenses, where appropriate, improves market definitions, better assesses consumer effects, and more efficiently targets enforcement. In gaming, creative harms are better revealed by a creativity lens, the metrics shifting from price, output, and innovation alone, accounting instead for market structures, conduct, and regulatory choices affecting creative processes. Rather than valuing innovation solely for new products or technical advancements, this lens foregrounds the creative mechanisms contributing to real gamer value.

Neoclassical economists would argue that creativity is inherently subjective and unsuited for competition law, especially as it is harder to quantify than price. As an analytical tool, a creativity lens risks inconsistent or subjective enforcement. Competition law has been criticised as a

⁸⁰ Rebecca Kelly Slaughter, 'Inclusive Competition' (2021) 1(2) CPI Antitrust Chronicle, 10 <<https://www.competitionpolicyinternational.com/category/spring-2021-volume-1-number-2/>> accessed 1 July 2025.

⁸¹ Christy England, Paul Tobias, 'The Gig Economy by the Numbers' (NIFWR, 2019-2021 statistics, 2023) <<https://niwr.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Gig-Economy-By-The-Numbers-The-Institute-2023.pdf>> accessed 1 July 2025.

regulatory obstacle to innovation and having an anti-growth effect, with some calling for it to return to a more administrable and objective grounding.⁸² Creative value could be better protected and promoted through cultural policy and targeted funding, not antitrust intervention. There is also a risk of chilling the innovations authorities seek to promote by focusing on process: novel business strategies and efficiency-enhancing mergers could be interpreted as anti-creative, and therefore anti-competitive. Firms consequently become more risk-averse and innovate less, preferring to stick with current successful business models.

This paper considers these concerns to be valid but ultimately unconvincing. The line between subjectivity and objectivity is already blurred, with competition authorities increasingly moving beyond purely economic assessments to evaluate non-traditional harms, like consumer privacy,⁸³ and the marginalisation of sub-groups. Authorities have adapted, using new assessment toolkits like the OECD's gender-inclusive lens to increase legal certainty and enforcement quality.⁸⁴ Creativity, whilst complex, can be assessed through similarly structured frameworks and with competition law embracing the challenges of digital markets and social inequality; it can equally do so for gaming. Importantly, a creativity lens enhances, but does not replace, existing tools and legal standards. It augments analysis, with authorities interpreting familiar facts in ways that better reflect the reality of creative industries. It draws attention to the non-price dimensions of competition that are particularly relevant in gaming. Competition law aims to prevent restrictions and distortions of competition, arising from mergers, anti-competitive agreements and abuses of dominant positions. What is framed as 'innovation' under traditional frameworks may reflect homogenisation, franchise recycling, and exploitative monetisation practices that constrain gamer welfare. Creativity is clearly a medium of competition in gaming. If companies endanger creative processes with the effect of harming actors like indie studios and gamers, such practices fall within the legal scope. Cases like *Epic v Apple* and *Microsoft/Activision* indicate a willingness by regulators to protect gaming markets;⁸⁵ a creativity lens allows them to achieve that aim more effectively by treating creativity as a central dimension of competition.

⁸² Commission (n 34); BBC (n 35).

⁸³ Bundeskartellamt, Case B6-22/26 (Case Summary, 6 February 2019) <https://www.bundeskartellamt.de/SharedDocs/Entscheidung/EN/Fallberichte/Missbrauchsaufsicht/2019/B6-22-16.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=> accessed 1 July 2025.

⁸⁴ OECD, 'Gender Inclusive Competition Toolkit' (Report, 2023) <https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2023/09/gender-inclusive-competition-toolkit_60844c97.html> accessed 1 July 2025.

⁸⁵ James Clayton, 'Epic v Apple: What have we learned?' (BBC, 24 May 2021) <<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/technology-57232824>> accessed 1 August 2025.

Overall, this chapter has revealed three insights. First, a distinct group of consumers (gamers) value creativity, not just lower prices or more content. Ignoring this risks underenforcement as gaming's demand-side effects are mischaracterised. Second, traditional innovation metrics, such as the number of games released or superficial technical updates, enable creative stagnation, simulating innovation whilst reducing real dynamic competition, which occurs through creativity. Third, the law can adapt to better protect the gaming industry. As the next chapter shows, creative contributors risk being sidelined not by superior efficiency, but through exclusionary tactics and a competition regime which cannot properly protect them.

Innovation alone is an inadequate measure for creative markets like gaming. Consumer value lies not just in output but in creative processes. However, competition law, focused on price and innovation output, misses this. In response, this paper proposed a creativity lens – a framework to assess and protect the structures that support creative diversity and consumer participation. It recognises that true welfare includes access to diverse content and the ability to meaningfully participate through creative expression. To protect gaming, competition law must evolve. Creativity is not just cultural – it is competitive – and must be preserved as such.

4. Microsoft/Activision Blizzard Through a Creativity Lens

Microsoft's acquisition of Activision in 2023 reveals important insights for gaming and competition law. This chapter first summarises the transaction, then critically re-examines the merger through a creativity lens. It highlights how user and indie studio creativity was overlooked despite its significance, and how cloud gaming can harm the diversity, quality, and direction of innovation in gaming.

4.1. Case Summary

4.1.1. The First Transaction

On 18 January 2022, Microsoft announced that it was acquiring Activision. Six months later, the 'Competition and Markets Authority' (CMA) launched its Phase 1 investigation, later escalating to Phase 2 in September after finding a potential 'substantial lessening of competition' (SLC). The main concern, also identified by the EC, was that Microsoft could leverage popular Activision titles like 'Call of Duty' (CoD) to foreclose rival cloud gaming services.⁸⁶

⁸⁶ *Microsoft/Activision Blizzard*(n 9).

The EC accepted an undertaking from Microsoft to license Activision's games for streaming to rival cloud gaming services in the EEA for 10 years.⁸⁷ The CMA deemed this remedy too narrow as it excluded multi-game subscription services (e.g., those competing with Xbox Game Pass) and non-Windows platforms.⁸⁸ It also only permitted standardised terms rather than allowing for them to develop organically through competition.⁸⁹ Therefore, the CMA blocked the deal, issuing a Final Order preventing any future acquisitions for 10 years.⁹⁰ The parties later argued that new developments – a broader EC cloud-gaming licence, a CoD agreement with Sony, and fresh UK and US case information – amounted to material changes.⁹¹ The CMA disagreed, noting cloud gaming's infancy and susceptibility to harm, and the remedies' failure to address evolving competitive risks, thus upholding the Final Order.⁹²

4.1.2. The Second Transaction

Following this, Microsoft submitted a revised merger notification which, amongst other developments, proposed selling Activision's non-EEA cloud-streaming rights for 15 years to Ubisoft.⁹³ This allowed Ubisoft to license Activision's games to cloud gaming services, including Microsoft's, enabling competition to still develop.⁹⁴ Ubisoft may also license Activision's content under different business models and require Microsoft to provide versions of games on non-Windows operating systems, bypassing other SLC concerns.⁹⁵ Recognising this as a significant change eliminating Microsoft's exclusive control, the CMA reviewed the revised deal and accepted the undertakings in lieu (UILs) offered by the parties, allowing the transaction to move forward.

⁸⁷ European Commission, 'Mergers: Commission clears acquisition of Activision Blizzard by Microsoft, subject to conditions' (Press Release, 15 May 2023) <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_2705> accessed 5 August 2025.

⁸⁸ CMA, 'Microsoft/Activision Blizzard Final Report.' (26 April 2023), 4–5 <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/644939aa529eda00c3b0525/Microsoft_Activision_Final_Report_.pdf> accessed 19 July 2025 (hereafter 'Final Report').

⁸⁹ Final Report, [11.111].

⁹⁰ CMA, 'Microsoft/Activision Blizzard Final Order' (CMA Website, 22 August 2023) <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/64e3764a3309b7000d1c9bd7/Microsoft_Activision_-_Final_Order.pdf> accessed 5 August 2025.

⁹¹ CMA, 'Summary of Final Decision on possible material change of circumstances or special reason for deciding differently under section 41(3) of the Enterprise Act 2002' (22 August 2023), [4] <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/64e36e553309b7000d1c9bcb/MS_A_-_Summary_of_Final_Decision.pdf> accessed 5 July 2025.

⁹² *ibid* [14].

⁹³ CMA, 'Microsoft/Activision Blizzard (ex-cloud streaming rights) merger inquiry' (CMA Website, 22 August 2023) <<https://www.gov.uk/cma-cases/microsoft-slash-activision-blizzard-ex-cloud-streaming-rights-merger-inquiry>> accessed 1 August 2025.

⁹⁴ CMA, 'Microsoft submits new deal for review after CMA confirms original deal is blocked' (Press Release, 22 August 2023) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/news/microsoft-submits-new-deal-for-review-after-cma-confirms-original-deal-is-blocked>> accessed 5 August 2025.

⁹⁵ *ibid*.

What is clear is that the CMA prioritised innovation and outcomes in cloud gaming, with the analysis focusing on who distributes games and under what licences. However, this occurred without considering how cloud gaming influences user or indie studio creative processes. The case's remedies similarly focused on divestiture of streaming rights rather than on protecting creative processes for users and indie studios. As this chapter will show, overlooking creativity in gaming risks harming gamer welfare.

4.2. User Creativity

This paper has repeatedly emphasised the importance of user creativity (UC) as a process. From user-built maps and novel gameplay experiences in 'Fortnite', to post-launch quality control for multi-million-dollar titles like 'Cyberpunk', UC initiatives extend game lifespans and result in decentralised innovations that developers may lack the resources to produce centrally. Unlike traditional markets, gamers do not merely consume; they co-create. This contributory and co-participatory activity is difficult to capture through conventional competition analysis, yet it highlights two important considerations.

Firstly, it forms a vital part of the value chain because gamers care about, and actively seek, creative extensions to their favourite titles. This is reflected by the success of platforms like Nexus Mods.⁹⁶ Secondly, it is important to innovation competition as high-quality mods like 'Counter-Strike' can become global bestsellers. The EC's Horizontal Merger Guidelines,⁹⁷ and the CMA's Merger Assessment Guidelines,⁹⁸ both recognise innovation as a dimension of competition, but do not mention the processes leading to it. This suggests that a regulatory gap exists, which can be satisfactorily addressed by a creativity lens. Cloud gaming threatens to damage the competitive significance of UC by shifting end-user rights and controlling access to game code. Historically, games were reproduced via disc or downloadable copy, with the user being granted limited permissions to use a copy of the game for personal, non-commercial reasons, via the end-user licensing agreement or terms of service.⁹⁹ Streaming technology makes it nearly impossible to obtain the software layers necessary for modding, as the game is stored online instead of on a physical device, with gamers no longer in possession of a reproduction of the game code.¹⁰⁰ This makes games 'tamper-proof', which protects IP, but it also eliminates the legal rights to 'tinker' that gamers value and that copyright is intended to

⁹⁶ Nexus (n 79).

⁹⁷ European Commission, 'Guidelines on the assessment of horizontal mergers under the Council Regulation on the control of concentrations between undertakings' [2004] OJ C31/5, [8].

⁹⁸ CMA, 'Merger Assessment Guidelines' (2021), [2.18].

⁹⁹ Yasar (n 1) 13.

¹⁰⁰ *ibid.*

incentivise.¹⁰¹ Whilst developers that offer integrated modding tools or public game code partially reduce these barriers, allowing creativity to occur, cloud gaming still recentralises creative control. A creativity lens exposes the real risk: developers define the parameters of permissible UC and meaningful participation, with creative experimentation outside of platform bounds now impossible. After all, it is highly unlikely that ‘Counter-Strike’ would have emerged as quickly, and successfully, as it did in a purely cloud-streamed environment.

The CMA’s investigation in *Microsoft/Activision* did not meaningfully address UC. The Final Report did reference post-launch developments usually found in modding, such as player skins and map packs, which persisted after Microsoft’s acquisition of Minecraft. However, this concerned producer-supplied content, not UC.¹⁰² The CMA continued with foreclosure theories of harm related to game exclusivity and rival cloud platforms – legitimate concerns correct to be pursued, but unfortunately too narrow to truly capture and assess the gaming market. Instead, the CMA undertook a traditional competition approach, investigating whether the merger would harm choice by making popular game franchises like CoD exclusive to Microsoft’s cloud gaming platforms.¹⁰³ Whilst important, there was no discussion of how cloud gaming and IP consolidation could harm creative processes like UC directly; the focus remained on outcomes only. This is supported by the CMA’s approach to consumers, whom the report correctly identified as ‘gamers’ but assessed only in terms of ultimate harms, not creative ones.¹⁰⁴ A creativity lens flips this analysis, asking first how creative agency and UC access are affected, then assessing how this shapes innovation and competition. Instead of preserving competition by emphasising ultimate harms against gamers, which under current methods is inadequate to encourage the creativity they value, it protects the processes that fuel the diversity, quality, and direction of innovation.

Nevertheless, the CMA’s approach has the benefit of remaining grounded in more administrable and predictable foreclosure theories with definable metrics like price and innovation, aligning with the current growth and deregulation agenda. Harms to process and creativity undermine deregulation through increased legal uncertainty, an outcome the government is increasingly pressuring the CMA to achieve the opposite of.¹⁰⁵ But whilst legal certainty is important, it should not come at the expense of effective analysis and enforcement. Even the Merger Guidelines on

¹⁰¹ Thomas (n 7) 13.

¹⁰² Final Report (n 88)[7.376].

¹⁰³ *ibid* [33], [48], [65].

¹⁰⁴ *ibid* [72].

¹⁰⁵ Department for Business & Trade, ‘Strategic steer to the Competition and Markets Authority’ (Policy Paper, 15 May 2025) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/strategic-steer-to-the-competition-and-markets-authority/strategic-steer-to-the-competition-and-markets-authority>> accessed 9 August 2025.

dynamic competition state that ‘uncertainty about the outcome of a dynamic competitive process does not preclude the CMA from assessing the impact of the merger on that dynamic process’.¹⁰⁶ Gaming is an inherently dynamic sector, characterised by innovation, and must be properly protected despite uncertainty concerns. The creativity lens has the advantage of supplementing, not displacing, orthodox approaches. In fact, improving analysis better aligns with a growth agenda than deregulation because the competitive process of gaming is better protected, and can therefore generate its real innovative value more easily. The creativity lens better captures the market and holds that gaming’s harms are creative and longer-term, not immediately apparent through price or innovation outcomes, yet central to competition assessments.

4.2.1. H2M and the Call of Duty Modding Ecosystem

This section proposes a creativity theory of harm to UC that was missed in *Microsoft/Activision*. The fan-made mod ‘H2M’ sought to breathe new life into an older Call of Duty release by integrating multiplayer support and updated graphics – but Activision’s cease-and-desist killed the project.¹⁰⁷ Their justification was that they were protecting their IP, ignoring that H2M was non-commercial, required ownership of the original title, and in fact boosted Activision’s revenues, driving the 2017 game back onto bestseller lists in 2024. Many argued the real reason was that Activision was worried about the competitive danger H2M posed to its upcoming release.¹⁰⁸ Gamers reacted with petitions, review bombing, and public criticism from major esports organisations, signalling that the mod was valuable to consumers and filled a market gap unmet by official releases.¹⁰⁹ H2M illustrates a broader structural shift in the gaming market, a deterioration of creative processes due to competitive concerns by incumbents. Historically, CoD has always had a vibrant modding scene. But as the series shifted to a live-service model, UC became restricted, and the channels enabling creative processes were increasingly controlled. So, when mods like H2M came out, with clear consumer value and demand, a creativity lens captures what traditional competition law does not: that a source of creativity

¹⁰⁶ CMA ‘Merger Guidelines’ (n 98)[5.20].

¹⁰⁷ Michael Cripe, ‘Modern Warfare 2 Multiplayer Mod Cancelled the Day Before Launch After Activision Sends Devs Cease and Desist’ (IGN, 16 August 2024) <<https://www.ign.com/articles/modern-warfare-2-multiplayer-mod-canceled-the-day-before-launch-after-activision-sends-devs-cease-and-desist>> accessed 20 July 2025.

¹⁰⁸ Ali Shutler, ‘Banned ‘Call Of Duty’ mod claims Activision were worried about the competition’ (NME, 19 August 2024) <<https://www.nme.com/news/gaming-news/banned-call-of-duty-mod-claims-activision-were-worried-about-the-competition-3784872>> accessed 19 July 2025.

¹⁰⁹ Rahman Shaukat, ‘Call of Duty: MW2 H2M Creator Explains Why Activision Shut Down Mod’ (Game Rant, 18 August 2024) <<https://gamerant.com/call-of-duty-mw2-h2m-mod-creator-why-activision-shut-down/>> accessed 19 July 2025.

and innovation was extinguished, not because of quality issues or consumer harm, but because of control over IP and a need to suppress competition.

Cloud gaming exacerbates these modding harms, as seen in the ‘Stop Killing Games’ (SKG) campaign with 1.4 million Europeans signing their petition, rallying against the practice of ‘killing’ games.¹¹⁰ Despite it being a consumer protection issue, SKG reflects the growing trend of publishers delisting or disabling access to previously purchased titles, usually on live-service or cloud games. The video games are sold as goods, with no stated expiration date, but are designed to be completely unplayable as soon as support from the publisher ends. This paper argues that this is relevant to competition as SKG does not just reflect lost access, but also a risk of terminating the possibility of modification and replayability, which generates additional competition and creative value.

Mergers like *Microsoft/Activision*, and the increasing move towards cloud gaming, exemplify this. By consolidating Activision’s vast title library, Microsoft can control both the code and execution environment, so any attempt to mod or replay streamed titles can be blocked at source. Just as H2M was silenced by Activision, now a part of the Microsoft ecosystem, so too can other grassroots creativity. The increasing shift to cloud-based access eliminates the infrastructure necessary for UC – files, code, and local installations. When gamers lose the ability to own or tinker with their games, creative participation collapses. The CMA was successful in identifying the use of IP to harm competition through exclusivity, but its remedies fell short. True protection of UC in gaming requires enforceable commitments to open toolkits, local-install options, and copyright preservation rights that prevent the kind of process foreclosure exemplified by H2M.

4.3. Indie Studio Creativity

Microsoft/Activision focused on the potential foreclosure of rival cloud gaming platforms and the games of AAA studios. However, it did not assess how cloud gaming infrastructures and IP consolidation could harm indie studios’ creative processes and their access to creative tools and important distribution platforms – despite the competitive and consumer value they bring.

The CMA concentrated much of its analysis on how the offering of AAA titles like ‘CoD’ and ‘World of Warcraft’ could affect competition in console and cloud gaming.¹¹¹ However, no reference is made to how indie studios are affected. They are only mentioned three times in the 418-page

¹¹⁰ Ross Scott, ‘Stop Killing Games’ (Campaign site) <<https://www.stopkillinggames.com/>> accessed 20 July 2025.

¹¹¹ Final Report (n 88) 4.

Final Report, concentrated in the industry background section, not competition assessments.¹¹² Despite the CMA defining the game publishing services market as ‘overall’, including indie studios,¹¹³ the focus of the report remains on the major AAA titles which generate millions of dollars of revenue. Through a creativity lens, the omission of indie studios would be significant as they generate vital creative processes and improve the diversity of innovation. In a recent survey, not only had 75% of those asked purchased digital indie game titles, but their predominant reason for doing so was creativity.¹¹⁴ Cloud gaming can harm indie studio creativity in various ways, largely as process constraints. As the CMA focused on how the merger would affect competition between major firms, it neglected the creative processes or competitive value of indie firms, differing from AAA studios not only in size, but also in creative method. Indie studio creativity is reliant on iteration, player feedback, and experimental, community-driven development cycles. Yet cloud gaming, as structured by dominant platforms like Microsoft, introduces new dependencies and restrictions that undermine these foundational aspects.

For example, AAA studios likely have the budget to include formal game testing departments in their own development cycles, which serve as a feedback tool, independent of cloud gaming, to gain critical user insights before release. Contrastingly, indie games will often first release as early-access betas, relying on user comments and continuous updates to achieve their desired quality. Interviews with indie developers indicate that building and engaging a strong community is a key theme, crucial for the success of their games; a primary means of doing so is the provision of free content, helping build trust and engagement.¹¹⁵ Cloud gaming platforms, owned by large companies maximising shareholder value, are where many of these indie games will release. They are unlikely to accommodate these indie studio strategies, as their games will take up server space and money whilst remaining unreleased. Crucially, the indie studios are unlikely to be making money, and, without investment, they cannot fund cloud access.

Microsoft has been known to finance developer projects in return for their inclusion on their cloud platform, ‘Xbox Game Pass’, which can initially reduce the significance of these concerns. However, because profit is generated through usage-based payments, there is a risk that cloud gaming accelerates indie studios’ development cycles, pulling them away from their creativity

¹¹² *ibid* [4.16].

¹¹³ *ibid* [5.139].

¹¹⁴ Jessica Clement, ‘Reasons for PC gamers in the United States and United Kingdom (UK) to play indie games as of October 2023’ (Statista, 15 February 2024) <<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1451137/indie-games-play-reason-pc-gamer/>> accessed 21 July 2025.

¹¹⁵ Jessica Mobley, ‘Effective Marketing and Monetization Strategies Used in Small Independent Game Development’ (2025) 1 Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies, 74 <<https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/16963/>> accessed 6 August 2025.

and autonomy and towards meeting corporate deadlines.¹¹⁶ Although gamers will play the releases more quickly – thereby increasing Microsoft’s revenue – they lose out on the creativity that might have emerged had indie studios retained greater creative independence. The prevalence of this is contested, but Microsoft itself admitted that there is a decline in base game sales 12 months after their addition to Game Pass.¹¹⁷ This suggests that either more creative titles are released, and competition is strong, or that players are not being long-term engaged by original experiences, because of rushed development. With the current creative stagnation, exemplified by Ubisoft, the latter is more likely.

Microsoft provides other indie programmes like ‘ID@Xbox’, leading to the release of over 1,000 titles and over \$5 billion in royalties to developers – supported by cloud gaming and pro-competitive from an innovation perspective.¹¹⁸ Still, the selection process is opaque and discretionary, and participation may require compliance with technical or monetisation frameworks. Also, ID@Xbox, whilst positive from an innovation or outcome perspective, misses the harms that occur before release. As Whitehouse contends, the abilities to analyse, preserve, and reverse-engineer games are vital learning tools for aspiring developers, insights that disappear when data and code are locked behind cloud servers.¹¹⁹ Although cloud gaming improves distribution efficiency and piracy protection, the loss of access to game code impedes creative education. It stifles the grassroots innovation that fundamentally shapes what the game becomes and who is allowed to meaningfully participate.

Therefore, from the innovation or outcome perspective, cloud gaming is positive. It can be a useful technology, helping bring indie studios to market, reducing costs and increasing gamer choice. But through a creativity lens, it can be the opposite: disrupting the access of indie studios to game code and forcing platform compliance. The current market trend is increasingly headed towards cloud gaming, with 55% of games already based on access, not ownership.¹²⁰ Gamers value the benefits that cloud gaming brings, and it is not an inherently harmful nor anti-competitive technology. However, caution must be exercised regarding the creative constraints

¹¹⁶ James Batchelor, ‘Xbox experimenting with how to pay studios for Game Pass “because we don’t think we have it figured out” (Games Industry, 25 November 2020) <<https://www.gamesindustry.biz/xbox-experimenting-with-how-to-pay-studios-for-game-pass-because-we-dont-think-we-have-it-figured-out>> accessed 5 August 2025.

¹¹⁷ Final Report (n 88)[5.60].

¹¹⁸ Guy Richards, ‘ID@Xbox: Developers of All Sizes Are Finding More Success With Xbox – \$5 Billion Paid Out to Date’ (Microsoft, 18 March 2025) <<https://news.xbox.com/en-us/2025/03/18/idxbox-developers-finding-success-with-xbox/>> accessed 6 August 2025.

¹¹⁹ Rich Whitehouse, ‘Streaming and Cloud Computing Endanger Modding and Game Preservation’ (Vice, 20 March 2019) <<https://www.vice.com/en/article/google-stadia-game-streaming-game-history-and-modding/>> accessed 19 July 2025.

¹²⁰ ERA, ‘Yearbook’ (ERA, 5 March 2025), 17 <<https://www.eraltd.org/yearbook>> accessed 21 July 2025.

it can impose on indie studios. A creativity lens centres this problem, not only analysing price effects or the number of indie games on cloud platforms but asking how business conduct or prospective mergers affect the conditions of indie studio creativity. If the answers to these questions are anti-creative, the danger is not only that competition is distorted, but that gaming's creativity is increasingly eroded.

With the CMA's failure to consider how cloud gaming may foreclose creative pathways for indie studios, they missed a vital layer of harm. Indie studios are not merely fringe businesses, instead they constitute a considerable bulk of the market in terms of quantity, quality, and market revenue. As cloud gaming becomes more dominant, the danger is that they will have to increasingly tailor their output to the technical and commercial frameworks of a few providers. Consequently, they lose the attributes that make them a more competitive force. To preserve quality gaming innovation, regulators must expand their scope. A creativity lens does not oppose technical progress like cloud gaming, instead requiring that key creative processes like indie studio development are accounted for, not harmed by negative changes to infrastructure or game development. Cloud gaming should not be allowed to become a bottleneck through which all innovation must pass. For indie developers, platform diversity, ease of entry, and retention of creative control are not luxuries but competitive necessities – regulators must act accordingly.

Concluding, some will contend that creative processes are a niche concern. Sticking to a traditional enforcement approach is less burdensome and provides for easier analysis. However, this paper has supported the stance that the CMA did not make an error in principle but neglected to account for creativity, the real value-driver in gaming, by relying on an outdated and improper framework. It is effective in conventional industries, but ill-equipped to capture innovation harms that arise in creative and community-driven industries. A creativity lens makes visible what the orthodox obscures: the processes which lead to gaming innovations, who pursues them, and under what conditions. Harms to competition and consumers do not just arise through platform foreclosure; they also occur through the restriction and control of creative pathways and competition law must recognise this. A creativity lens does not discard the toolkit; it expands it to allow for a better mapping of gaming and prioritises not just innovation's outcomes, but also its diversity, quality, and direction – which gamers value.

5. Conclusion

This paper began with the observation that competition law treats 'more content' as synonymous with 'more innovation' whilst overlooking the conditions that allow creative processes to flourish. By critically examining gaming's structure, actors, and regulatory treatment, it revealed

that this reality is dangerous. Gaming's value and competitiveness stems from the diversity, autonomy, and openness of creative processes, as well as technological advances and increased output. When creativity is suppressed, gamer welfare is diminished, even if conventional innovation metrics find consumer welfare to be positive.

Chapter 2 demonstrated that the current focus on outcome shows that R&D spend, patent activity, and product output are blunt instruments, carried over from innovation analysis in non-creative industries and capturing neither the source nor quality of creativity. This makes it possible for incumbents to appear innovative whilst recycling the same game formulas and monetisation strategies as evidenced by the TVGS v Ubisoft case. A solo-developed yet creative title outperformed a developer giant because it offered an originality that resonated with players, displeased with the lack of originality in AAA studios' output.

Chapter 3 established that creativity and innovation, though related, are distinct. Creativity is an original process, often iterative and collaborative, whose value is not dependent on commercialisation. Gamers noticeably care about this process, whether through modding, community-led design, or indie studios, yet current enforcement approaches rarely acknowledge creativity as a competitive parameter. This omission means that harms to gamer welfare – understood as encompassing not only price but creativity – are often left unaddressed.

The *Microsoft/Activision* case study in Chapter 4 reinforced the lack of creativity's capture during enforcement: the CMA's orthodox foreclosure theory left unexamined how cloud gaming and IP consolidation threatens the creative processes of users and indie studios. As a result, the diversity, quality, and direction of innovation in gaming is compromised. Traditional analysis frames developments like removing modding opportunities and reducing the creative autonomy of indie studios as harmless, unless they produce measurable effects on outcomes. But this misses the real issue – that creative harms are competitive harms, eroding the mechanisms responsible for the dynamism of the gaming industry.

Therefore, this paper has proposed a 'creativity lens' as both an analytical tool and a means of achieving better remedies. It broadens the scope of competition without abandoning established standards by integrating considerations of the openness, autonomy, and diversity of creative processes alongside outcome-based measures of innovation. This approach would have sharpened the CMA's understanding of gaming in *Microsoft/Activision*, prompting further scrutiny of its impact on user creativity and indie studios. Crucially, a creativity lens does not automatically proscribe mergers or dominant conduct by anyone except indie studios and users; rather, it ensures that any changes affecting indie games or user creativity are also assessed.

This enforcement approach could require merging parties to continue to facilitate modding through local-install options or public code, and maintain platform diversity for indie titles, as well as AAA ones. Creative process foreclosure could be identified as a distinct theory of harm, grounded in the competitive value of those processes.

Looking forward, there is reason for both caution and optimism. Cloud gaming subscription models will likely become more common, increasing the barriers to creative participation. Without intervention, the market risks moving towards a homogenised, high-output, low-creativity scenario. Still, that same development, if properly regulated, can lower distribution costs, expand the reach of indie studios, and potentially foster new forms of co-creation. The industry is at a crossroads; its innovative direction dependent on whether competition law recognises that creativity is a competitive parameter worth protecting.

Indeed, there are limits to what this research has achieved. The creativity lens remains at an early conceptual stage and full operationalisation requires clear competitive indicators, a willingness by regulators to engage, and toolkits to guide enforcement and increase predictability. This paper has neither attempted to resolve the challenges of measuring creativity, nor assessed fully how a creativity lens would operate in practice. Undoubtedly, these are important areas that future research can address. However, this paper has provided a strong foundation supporting its inclusion. The creativity lens better safeguards the cultural and economic value of gaming, ensuring that future innovation is not only plentiful but meaningful.

Bibliography

Articles

Aghion P et al., 'Competition and Innovation: An Inverted-U Relationship (2005) 120(2) The Quarterly Journal of Economics 701

Castillo-Vergara M et al., 'The Creative Process and Innovation: The Role of Knowledge Management and Industrial Cluster' (2022) 26(6) International Journal of Innovation Management 1

Cropley D et al., 'Measuring Creativity for Innovation Management' (2011) 6(3) Journal of Technology Management & Innovation 14

Deutscher E, Makris S, 'Sustainability concerns in EU merger control: from output-maximising to polycentric innovation competition' (2023) 11 Journal of Antitrust Enforcement 350

Dunne N, 'Public Interest and EU Competition Law' (2020) 65(2) The Antitrust Bulletin 256

Ishihara M, Rietveld J, 'The Effect of Acquisitions on Product Innovativeness, Quality, and Sales Performance: Evidence from the Console Video Game Industry (2002-2010)' (2017) 1 Academy of Management Proceedings <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2897264> accessed 29 July 2025

Lianos I, 'Polycentric Competition Law' (2018) 71(1) Current Legal Problems 161

Martinez A, 'A Fortnite and Odd Days: The Console Wars' (2022) 6(2) Market and Competition Law Review 51

Mehra S, Zuercher J, 'Striking Out "Competitive Balance" in Sports, Antitrust, and Intellectual Property' (2006) 21(4) Berkeley Technology Law Journal 1499

Mobley J, 'Effective Marketing and Monetization Strategies Used in Small Independent Game Development' (2025) 1 Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies <<https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/16963/>> accessed 6 August 2025

Slaughter R K, 'Inclusive Competition' (2021) 1(2) CPI Antitrust Chronicle <<https://www.competitionpolicyinternational.com/category/spring-2021-volume-1-number-2/>> accessed 1 July 2025

Thomas A et al., 'Competition in the cloud gaming market: proposing the innovation-creativity dichotomy' (2025) 8(2) Interactive Entertainment Law Review 1

White M, 'The Senescence of Creativity: How Market Forces are Killing Digital Games' (2009) 3(4) Loading... <<https://journals.sfu.ca/loading/index.php/loading/article/view/54>> accessed 29 July 2025

Yasar A et al., 'Gaming Without Frontiers: Copyright and Competition in the Changing Video Game Sector' (CREATe Working Paper 2023/10, 2023) <<https://eprints.gla.ac.uk/307648/2/307648.pdf>> accessed 10 July 2025

Chapters In Books and Books

Budzinski O, Feddersen A, 'Should Organising Premier-Level European Football Be A Monopoly? And Who Should Run It? – An Economists' Perspective' in Jacob Kornbeck (ed), *EU Antitrust Law and Sport Governance* (1st ed, Routledge 2022)

Christie A, 'Creativity and Innovation: A Legal Perspective' in Leon Mann and Janet Chan (eds), *Creativity and Innovation in Business and Beyond: Social Science Perspectives and Policy Implications* (1st ed, Routledge 2011)

Forgang W, Einolf K, *Management Economics: An Accelerated Approach* (1st ed, Routledge 2015)

Gürkaynak G, *Innovation Paradox in Merger Control* (1st ed, Concurrences 2023)

OECD/EuroStat, *Oslo Manual 2018* (4th ed, OECD Publishing 2018) <https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2018/10/oslo-manual-2018_g1g9373b/9789264304604-en.pdf> accessed 9 July 2025

Schumpeter J, *Capitalism, Socialism, and Democracy* (1st ed, Routledge 2003), <<https://periferiaactiva.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/joseph-schumpeter-capitalism-socialism-and-democracy-2006.pdf>> accessed 9 August 2025

Zackariasson P, Wilson T, 'The Role of the Consumer: From Sales to Co-production' in Sabine Hotho and Neil McGregor (eds), *Changing the Rules of the Game* (1st ed, Palgrave Macmillan 2013)

Cases

Bayer/Monsanto (Case COMP/M.8084) [2018] 1709 final

CMA Microsoft/Activision Blizzard (ex-cloud streaming rights) Merger Inquiry

CMA Microsoft/Activision Blizzard Merger Inquiry

David Meca-Medina and Igor Majcen v Commission of the European Communities (Case C-519/04) [2006] ECR I-06991

Dow/DuPont (Case COMP/M.7932)[2017] OJ C353/9

Facebook, Exploitative business terms pursuant to Section 19(1) GWB for inadequate data processing (B6-22/16, Bundeskartellamt Decision of 6 February 2019)

Intel Corporation Inc v Commission (Case C-413/14)[2017] OJ C374/2

Microsoft/Activision Blizzard (Case M.10646)[2023] 3199 final

Conferences

ICN, 'Competition Enforcement and Consumer Welfare' (ICN Conference, Hague, May 2011) <https://www.internationalcompetitionnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/SP_CWelfare2011.pdf> accessed 2 August 2025

Scacchi W, 'Modding as a basis for developing game systems' (33rd International Conference on Software Engineering, Honolulu, May 2011) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/1984674.1984677>> accessed 7 August 2025

Legislation, Guidelines, and Regulations

CMA, 'Merger Assessment Guidelines' (2021) CMA129

Competition Act 1998

Consolidated version of the Treaty on European Union [2012] OJ C326/13

European Commission, 'Guidelines on the applicability of Article 101 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union to horizontal co-operation agreements' [2023] OJ C259/1

European Commission, 'Guidelines on the assessment of horizontal mergers under the Council Regulation on the control of concentrations between undertakings' [2004] OJ C31/5

Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act)[2022] OJ L 265/1

Websites

Batchelor J, 'Xbox experimenting with how to pay studios for Game Pass "because we don't think we have it figured out"' (Games Industry, 25 November 2020) <<https://www.gamesindustry.biz/xbox-experimenting-with-how-to-pay-studios-for-game-pass-because-we-dont-think-we-have-it-figured-out>> accessed 5 August 2025

Burt D, 'FromSoftware's Influence: A Legacy of Challenge and Discovery' (Brig Newspaper, 7 March 2025) <<https://brignews.com/2025/03/07/fromsoftwares-influence-a-legacy-of-challenge-and-discovery/>> accessed 9 July 2025

Capobianco A, 'The Relationship between Competition and Innovation' (Note by Austria, 14 June 2023) <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD\(2023\)5/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD(2023)5/en/pdf)> accessed 9 July 2025

Clayton J, 'Epic v Apple: What have we learned?' (BBC, 24 May 2021) <<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/technology-57232824>> accessed 1 August 2025

Clement J, 'Reasons for PC gamers in the United States and United Kingdom (UK) to play indie games as of October 2023' (Statista, 15 February 2024) <<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1451137/indie-games-play-reason-pc-gamer/>> accessed 21 July 2025

Clement J, 'Video game industry - Statistics & Facts' (Statista, 6 November 2024) <<https://www.statista.com/topics/868/video-games/#topicOverview>> accessed 8 August 2025

CMA, 'Microsoft / Activision Blizzard (ex-cloud streaming rights) merger inquiry' (CMA Website, 22 August 2023) <<https://www.gov.uk/cma-cases/microsoft-slash-activision-blizzard-ex-cloud-streaming-rights-merger-inquiry>> accessed 1 August 2025

CMA, 'Microsoft submits new deal for review after CMA confirms original deal is blocked' (Press Release, 22 August 2023) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/news/microsoft-submits-new-deal-for-review-after-cma-confirms-original-deal-is-blocked>> accessed 5 August 2025

CMA, 'Microsoft/Activision Blizzard Final Order' (CMA Website, 22 August 2023) <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/64e3764a3309b7000d1c9bd7/Microsoft_Activision_-_Final_Order.pdf> accessed 5 August 2025

CMA, 'Microsoft/Activision Blizzard Final Report.' (26 April 2023) <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/644939aa529eda000c3b0525/Microsoft_Activision_Final_Report_.pdf> accessed 19 July 2025

CMA, 'Microsoft/Activision Blizzard merger inquiry' (CMA Website, 6 July 2022) <<https://www.gov.uk/cma-cases/microsoft-slash-activision-blizzard-merger-inquiry>> accessed 29 July 2025

CMA, 'Summary of Final Decision on possible material change of circumstances or special reason for deciding differently under section 41(3) of the Enterprise Act 2002' (22 August 2023)

<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/64e36e553309b7000d1c9bcb/MS_A_-_Summary_of_Final_Decision.pdf> accessed 5 August 2025

Cripe M, 'Modern Warfare 2 Multiplayer Mod Cancelled the Day Before Launch After Activision Sends Devs Cease and Desist' (IGN, 16 August 2024) <<https://www.ign.com/articles/modern-warfare-2-multiplayer-mod-canceled-the-day-before-launch-after-activision-sends-devs-cease-and-desist>> accessed 20 July 2025

Department for Business & Trade, 'Strategic steer to the Competition and Markets Authority' (Policy Paper, 15 May 2025) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/strategic-steer-to-the-competition-and-markets-authority/strategic-steer-to-the-competition-and-markets-authority>> accessed 9 August 2025

Draghi M, 'The future of European competitiveness' (Part A, 9 September 2024) <https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/97e481fd-2dc3-412d-be4c-f152a8232961_en?filename=The%20future%20of%20European%20competitiveness%20_%20A%20competitiveness%20strategy%20for%20Europe.pdf> accessed 2 August 2025

Dutta A, 'Does Assassin's Creed Shadows Feature Microtransactions?' (DeltiasGaming, 21 March 2025) <<https://deltiasgaming.com/does-assassins-creed-shadows-feature-microtransactions/>> accessed 1 July 2025

England C, Tobias P, 'The Gig Economy by the Numbers' (NIFWR, 2019-2021 statistics, 2023) <https://niwr.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Gig-Economy-By-The-Numbers-The-Institute_2023.pdf> accessed 1 July 2025

ERA, 'Yearbook' (ERA, 5 March 2025) <<https://www.eraltd.org/yearbook>> accessed 21 July 2025

European Commission, 'A Competitiveness Compass for the EU' (Communication, 29 January 2025) <https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/10017eb1-4722-4333-add2-e0ed18105a34_en?filename=Communication_1.pdf> accessed 2 August 2025

European Commission, 'Mergers: Commission clears acquisition of Activision Blizzard by Microsoft, subject to conditions' (Press Release, 15 May 2023) <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_2705> accessed 5 August 2025

European Commission, 'Review of the Merger Guidelines: Topic C' (EC Website, 2025) <https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/mergers/review-merger-guidelines_en> accessed 5 July 2025

Greffe X, 'Managing Creative Enterprises' (WIPO Creative Industries Booklet No 3, December 2006) <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/copyright/938/wipo_pub_938.pdf#:~:text=later%20when%20the%20product%20is,as%20well%20as%20their%20own> accessed 9 July 2025

Hussain A, 'How the Video Game Industry Is Changing' (Investopedia, 26 April 2025) <<https://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/053115/how-video-game-industry-changing.asp>> accessed 28 July 2025

Jack S, Edwards C, 'Government ousts UK competition watchdog chair' (BBC, 21 January 2025) <<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/c2d3e6zklxg>> accessed 1 July 2025

Julizar A, 'How Ubisoft Lost Its Way - A Gamer's Lament and a Business Lesson For Us' (Medium, 8 October 2024) <<https://allenherlambang.medium.com/how-ubisoft-lost-its-way-a-gamers-lament-and-a-business-lesson-for-us-2956ee44049b>> accessed 1 July 2025

Kelion L, 'Assassin's Creed: Unity criticised for widespread glitches' (BBC, 13 November 2014) <<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/technology-30040613>> accessed 30 June 2025

Marcusa A, 'I'm tired of Ubisoft selling me the same game over and over' (Pocket-lint, 6 September 2024) <<https://www.pocket-lint.com/im-tired-of-ubisoft-selling-me-the-same-game-over-and-over/>> accessed 30 June 2025

MCV Staff, 'For Honor: Everything you need to know' (MCVUK, 3 February 2017) <<https://mcvuk.com/business-news/publishing/for-honor-everything-you-need-to-know-release-date-price-beta-and-season-pass-info-merchandise-and-pre-order-deals/>> accessed 30 June 2025

Mitra R, 'Indie Games that Became Major Success Stories' (30 December 2024) <<https://gamerant.com/indie-games-major-success-stories/>> accessed 9 July 2025

Nexus, 'Nexus Mods' (Nexus Mods Homepage, Statistics from 26 July 2025) <<https://www.nexusmods.com>> accessed 26 July 2025

OECD, 'Advantages and Disadvantages of Competition Welfare Standards' (Note by BIAC, 15 June 2023) <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD\(2023\)30/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD(2023)30/en/pdf)> accessed 31 July 2025

OECD, 'Gender Inclusive Competition Toolkit' (Report, 2023) <https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2023/09/gender-inclusive-competition-toolkit_60844c97.html> accessed 1 July 2025

OECD, 'The Consumer Welfare Standard - Advantages and Disadvantages Compared to Alternative Standards (Background Note, 25 April 2023) <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP\(2023\)4/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP(2023)4/en/pdf)> accessed 7 August 2025

OECD, 'The Relationship Between Competition and Innovation' (BIAC Note, 14 June 2023) <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD\(2023\)56/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/WD(2023)56/en/pdf)> accessed 9 July 2025

Orland K, 'Analysis: For Honor unlocks cost \$730 (or 5,200 hours)' (ArsTechnica, 21 March 2017) <<https://arstechnica.com/gaming/2017/03/analysis-for-honor-unlocks-cost-730-or-5200-hours/>> accessed 30 June 2025

Osborne M, 'Cyberpunk 2077 Fans Are Fixing The Game Themselves' (SVG, 8 February 2021) <<https://www.svg.com/329720/cyberpunk-2077-fans-are-fixing-the-game-themselves/>> accessed 4 August 2025

Pabón A, Capobianco A, 'Competition and Innovation, Part I: a theoretical perspective' (OECD Background Note, 2 May 2023) 7 <[https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP\(2023\)2/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP(2023)2/en/pdf)> accessed 28 July 2025

Richards G, 'ID@Xbox: Developers of All Sizes Are Finding More Success With Xbox - \$5 Billion Paid Out to Date' (Microsoft, 18 March 2025) <<https://news.xbox.com/en-us/2025/03/18/idxbox-developers-finding-success-with-xbox/>> accessed 6 August 2025

Scott R, 'Stop Killing Games' (Campaign site) <<https://www.stopkillinggames.com/>> accessed 20 July 2025

Shaukat R, 'Call of Duty: MW2 H2M Creator Explains Why Activision Shut Down Mod' (Game Rant, 18 August 2024) <<https://gamerant.com/call-of-duty-mw2-h2m-mod-creator-why-activision-shut-down/>> accessed 19 July 2025

Shutler A, 'Banned 'Call Of Duty' mod claims Activision were worried about the competition' (NME, 19 August 2024) <<https://www.nme.com/news/gaming-news/banned-call-of-duty-mod-claims-activision-were-worried-about-the-competition-3784872>> accessed 19 July 2025

Smash JT, 'Schedule I Is Already More Popular Than Assassin's Creed Shadows...' (Smash JT, March 2025) <<https://www.smashjt.com/post/schedule-i-is-already-more-popular-than-assassin-s-creed-shadows>> accessed 9 July 2025

SteamDB, 'Assassin's Creed Shadows Steam Statistics' (SteamDB, 30 June 2025) <<https://steamdb.info/app/3159330/charts/>> accessed 30 June 2025

SteamDB, 'Schedule | Steam Statistics' (SteamDB, 30 June 2025) <<https://steamdb.info/app/3164500/>> accessed 30 June 2025

Stubbs M, 'The incredible rise of Dota' (Red Bull, 30 July 2019) <<https://www.redbull.com/int-en/the-history-of-dota>> accessed 2 August 2025

Video Game Insights, 'Global Indie Games Market Report 2024' (VGInsights, 13 October 2024) <https://vginsights.com/assets/reports/VGI_Global_Indie_Games_Market_Report_2024.pdf> accessed 21 July 2025

von Hippel E, 'The User Innovation Revolution' (MITSloan Management Review Interview, 21 September 2011) <<https://sloanreview.mit.edu/article/the-user-innovation-revolution/>> accessed 2 July 2025

Webster H, 'How many games has Ubisoft made?' (TheGamer, 14 October 2024) <<https://www.thegamer.com/how-many-games-ubisoft-made/>> accessed 30 June 2025

Whitehouse R, 'Streaming and Cloud Computing Endanger Modding and Game Preservation' (Vice, 20 March 2019) <<https://www.vice.com/en/article/google-stadia-game-streaming-game-history-and-modding/>> accessed 19 July 2025

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